

A REVIEW ON KACHHURAKSHAS TAIL

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ABSTRACT

Sneha Kalpana is a unique pharmaceutical procedure in Ayurveda that enhances the therapeutic efficacy of drugs by facilitating the extraction of lipid-soluble active principles. *Kachhuraksas Taila* is a classical herbo-mineral formulation described in Ayurvedic literature and widely used in the management of *Kusṭha* (skin disorders), *Kandu* (pruritus), *Vraṇa* (wounds), *sotha* (inflammation), and *Krimi* (infective conditions).^[1] The formulation contains drugs possessing *Usṇa virya*, *Tikṣṇa guṇa*, and *Kuṣṭhaghna–Krimighna* properties, processed in a suitable oil base. Special pharmaceutical procedures such as *Sodhana* and appropriate *Sneha Paka* ensure safety and therapeutic effectiveness. This review aims to compile classical references, ingredient details and probable mode of action of *Kachhuraksas Taila*. The formulation shows significant potential due to its antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties. Further scientific and clinical studies are required to validate its traditional claims.

KEYWORDS: *Sneha Kalpana*, *Kachhuraksas Taila*, *Kuṣṭha*, Medicated oil.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is one of the oldest traditional systems of medicine, based on experiential knowledge and rational therapeutic principles. *Bhaishajya Kalpana*, the branch of Ayurveda dealing with pharmaceutical preparations, emphasizes not only the formulation of medicines

such as *Churṇa*, *Vaṭi*, *Avaleha*, *Asava*, *Ariṣṭa*, and *Sneha*, but also quality control from raw material collection to finished products.

Sneha Kalpana is an important secondary dosage form in which drugs in the form of *Kalka* and *Drava dravya* are processed with *sneha dravya* according to the classical ratio described by Acharya Saarnghadhara.^[2] *Sneha* preparations can be administered internally as *Paana*, *Basti*, *Nasya*, and externally as *Abhyanga* and *Lepana*.

Kachhuraksas Taila is a classical herbo-mineral medicated oil indicated mainly for *Kuṣṭha roga* and allied skin disorders. The formulation contains drugs with potent *Kuṣṭhaghna*, *Krimighna*, *Sothahara*, and *Vraṇa-ropaka* properties. Due to the presence of volatile and heat-sensitive ingredients, traditional pharmaceutical principles emphasize careful processing to preserve therapeutic efficacy. *Kachhuraksas Taila* is primarily used for external application, especially in chronic and recurrent dermatological conditions.

Ingredients of Kachhurakshas Taila

S. No.	Drug	Botanical / English Name	Rasa	Guṇa	Virya	Vipaka	Karma
A) Kalka Dravya							
1.	Manashila	<i>Arsenic sulphide</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Kuṣṭhaghna, Krimighna
2.	Haratala	<i>Arsenic sulphide</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Kuṣṭhaghna
3.	Kasisa	<i>Ferrous sulphate</i>	Kasaya, Amla	Laghu, Rukṣa	Usṇa	Amla	Raktavardhaka
4.	Suddha Gandhaka	<i>Sulphur</i>	Madhura	Snigdha	Usṇa	Madhura	Rasayana, Kuṣṭhaghna
5.	Saindhava Lavaṇa	Rock salt	Lavaṇa	Laghu, Snigdha	Sita	Madhura	Tridosaghna
6.	Svarṇaksiri	<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Virecaka
7.	Pashaṇabheda	<i>Bergenia ligulata</i>	Tikta, Kasaya	Laghu	Sita	Kaṭu	Ashmaribhed
8.	Suṅṭhi	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Kaṭu	Laghu, Snigdha	Usṇa	Madhura	Dipana
9.	Kuṣṭha	<i>Saussurea lappa</i>	Tikta, Kaṭu	Laghu, Rukṣa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Kuṣṭhaghna
10.	Pippali	<i>Piper longum</i>	Kaṭu	Laghu, Snigdha	Anusṇa	Madhura	Rasayana
11.	Langali	<i>Gloriosa superba</i>	Tikta, Kaṭu	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Viśaghna
12.	Karavira	<i>Nerium indicum</i>	Tikta, Kasaya	Laghu	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Krimighna

13.	Cakramarda	<i>Cassia tora</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Kuṣṭhaghna
14.	Viḍanga	<i>Embelia ribes</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Ruksa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Krimighna
15.	Citraka	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Kaṭu	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Agnidipaka
16.	Danti	<i>Baliospermum montanum</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Virecaka
17.	Nimba	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Tikta, Kasaya	Laghu, Ruksa	Sita	Kaṭu	Raktaprasadana
B) Sneha Dravya							
1.	Sarsapa Taila	Mustard oil	Kaṭu, Tikta	Tikṣṇa, Snigdha	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Kaphavata Samaka, Krimighna
C) Drava Dravya							
1.	Gomutra	Cow urine	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Lekhana
2.	Arka	<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Kaṭu, Tikta	Laghu, Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Sothahara
3.	Snuhi	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i>	Kaṭu	Tikṣṇa	Usṇa	Kaṭu	Virecaka
4.	Jala	Water	Avyakta	Laghu	Sita	Madhura	Jivana

Sarsapa Taila (Mustard Oil) is obtained from Sarsapa (*Brassica nigra*) and is widely used in Ayurveda for both internal and external purposes. It possesses Kaṭu and Tikta rasa, Tikṣṇa and Snigdha guṇa, Usṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is predominantly KaphavataSamaka and is extensively used in skin disorders, wound management, massage therapy, and as a base oil in Sneha Kalpana.^[3]

Manashila (Realgar) is an arsenic sulphide mineral classified under Uparasa. It is Tikta–Kaṭu in rasa, Tikṣṇa in guṇa, Usṇa in virya and Kaṭu in vipaka. After proper Sodhana, it is used in Kuṣṭha, Krimi, and other chronic skin diseases.^[4]

Haratala (Orpiment) is another arsenic-based Uparasa dravya. It is Kaṭu–Tikta in rasa, Tikṣṇa guṇa, Usṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is mainly used externally and in Kuṣṭha, Kandu, and Krimi after purification.^[5]

Kasisa (Ferrous Sulphate) is an Upadhatu of Loha and an important mineral drug in Rasashastra. It has Kasaya–Amla rasa, Laghu–Ruksa guṇa, Usṇa virya and Amla vipaka. It is indicated in Paṇḍu, Rakta-ksaya and skin disorders.^[6]

Suddha Gandhaka (Sulphur) is the second most important drug after Parada in Rasashastra and is classified under Uparasa. It is Madhura rasa, Snigdha guṇa, Usṇa virya and Madhura vipaka. It is widely used in Kuṣṭha, Kasa, Svasa and Rasayana preparations.^[7]

Saindhava Lavaṇa (Rock Salt) is considered the best among all salts. It has Lavaṇa rasa, Laghu–Snigdha guṇa, Sita virya and Madhura vipaka. It is Tridosaghna and commonly used in digestive and respiratory disorders.^[8]

SvarṇaSiri (Swarnashiri) is identified botanically as *Argemone mexicana* Linn. of the family Papaveraceae. Its important synonyms include SvarṇaSiri and Hema-puspi. Classical texts describe its utility after proper purification in disorders such as Kuṣṭha, Kṛmi and Vraṇa. The plant contains alkaloids like berberine, protopine and sanguinarine. It exhibits Tikta and Kaṭu rasa, Laghu and Ruksa guṇa, Usṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. Clinically, it is used in Kuṣṭha, Kṛmi and Vraṇa.^[9]

Pashaṇabheda is botanically identified as *Bergenia ligulata* (Wall.) Engl., belonging to the family Saxifragaceae. Important synonyms of Pashaṇabheda include ashmaribheda, Silabheda and Nagabhid. In classical Ayurvedic literature, Pashaṇabheda is described as a prime drug in ashmari cikitsa due to its lithotriptic action and is commonly used in the form of Kwatha, Curṇa and Ghṛta preparations. Chemically, it contains bergenin, gallic acid, catechin and tannins. According to Ayurvedic pharmacodynamics, it possesses Tikta and Kasaya rasa, Laghu and Ruksa guṇa, Sita virya and Kaṭu vipaka. Therapeutically, it is indicated in ASmari, Mutrakṛcchra, Mutraghata, Prameha and Sotha.^[10]

Suṅṭhi (Dry Ginger) is obtained from *Zingiber officinale* and is widely used as a digestive stimulant. It possesses Kaṭu rasa, Laghu–Snigdha guṇa, Uṣṇa virya and Madhura vipaka. It is effective in Agnimandya, Ama, Kasa and Svasa.^[11]

Pippali (Long Pepper) is an important Rasayana drug described in Ayurveda. It has Kaṭu rasa, Laghu–Snigdha guṇa, Anuṣṇa virya and Madhura vipaka. It is used in respiratory disorders and as a bioavailability enhancer.^[12]

Langali (Laangli) is botanically known as *Gloriosa superba* Linn., belonging to the family Colchicaceae. Classical synonyms of Langali include Kalihari and Viṣaṇika. It is described as a Viṣa dravya in Ayurvedic texts and is administered only in purified form. The major chemical constituents present in Langali are colchicine and gloriosine. Pharmacodynamically, it has Tikta and Kaṭu rasa, Laghu, Tikshna and Ruksa guṇa, Uṣṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. Therapeutically, it is indicated in Granthi, Arbuda, Sotha and for Artava-janana, though its use is strictly regulated due to high toxicity.^[13]

Karavira (Karvir) is identified botanically as *Nerium oleander* Linn. of the family Apocynaceae. Its important synonyms are Karavira, Asvamaraka and Raktapuspa. Karavira is classified under Upavisa dravya in Ayurveda and is used internally and externally only after proper Sodhana. The plant contains potent cardiac glycosides such as oleandrin and neriin. In terms of Rasa–Guṇa–Virya–Vipaka, Karavira possesses Tikta and Kaṭu rasa, Laghu and Tikshna guṇa, Uṣṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is indicated in Kuṣṭha, Kṛmi, Sotha and Granthi, and should be used with extreme caution due to its toxic nature.^[14]

Cakramarda (Chakramard) is botanically known as *Cassia tora* Linn., belonging to the family Caesalpiniaceae. Synonyms of Cakramarda include Dadamardaka, reflecting its specific action against Dadru. Classical Ayurvedic literature describes it as an effective Kuṣṭhaghna and Kṛmighna drug. The important chemical constituents of Cakramarda are chrysophanol, emodin and rhein. It possesses Kaṭu and Tikta rasa, Laghu and Ruksa guṇa, Uṣṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is therapeutically indicated in Dadru, Kuṣṭha, Kandu and Kṛmi.^[15]

Vidanga is botanically identified as *Embelia ribes* Burm. f., belonging to the family Primulaceae. The dried fruits are used medicinally. Vidanga possesses Kaṭu and Kashaya rasa, Laghu and Ruksha guṇa, Uṣṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is a well-known Kṛmighna

drug and also exhibits Dipana and Pachana properties. Vidanga is indicated in Krimi roga, Arsha, Grahani, Ajirna and Mandagni. Important formulations include Vidangarishta and various Krimighna yogas.^[16]

Chitrakmula is botanically identified as *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn., belongs to the family Plumbaginaceae. Present research work reveals that plumbagin obtained of *P. zeylanica* is a potent cytotoxic/anti-cancer agent. It is one of the main ingredients in Trimada, Panchkola and Shadushna. Major Chemical constituents present are Plumbagin, Chitranone, 3-chloroplumbagin, droserone, elliptinone, isozeylinone, isozeylan-one, zeylanone and zeylinone, maritone, plumbagic acid, dihydrosterone etc. It is indicated in treatment of various diseases like Arshas, Grahni, Udara, Krimi, Shula, Pandu, and Kasa.^[17]

Danti is botanically known as *Baliospermum montanum* (Willd.) Muell.-Arg., belonging to the family Euphorbiaceae. The root is the medicinally useful part. Danti has Katu and Tikta rasa, Guru and Tikshna guna, Ushna virya and Katu vipaka. It is a potent Rechana and Bhedana dravya indicated mainly in Udara, Shotha, Arsha, Gulma and Vibandha. Due to its strong purgative action, it should be administered carefully under medical supervision.^[18]

Nimba (Neem) is a well-known medicinal plant with Tikta–Kasaya rasa, Laghu–Ruksha guna, Sita virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is widely used in Kuṣṭha, Raktadosa and as a Krimighna drug.^[19]

Aragvadha, also known as Aaragvadh or Rajavriksha, is botanically identified as *Cassia fistula* Linn. and belongs to the family Fabaceae. The fruit pulp, root and bark are used therapeutically. Aragvadha possesses Madhura rasa, Guru and Snigdha guna, Sheeta virya and Madhura vipaka. It is a Mridu Virechaka and Shothahara drug indicated in Kustha, Jvara, Vibandha, Pitta roga and Rakta vikaras.

Gomutra (Cow Urine) is considered a potent therapeutic substance in Ayurveda. It possesses Kaṭu–Tikta rasa, Laghu–Tikshna guna, Uṣṇa virya and Kaṭu vipaka. It is used for Lekhana, Krimi-nashana and metabolic disorders.

Arka is botanically identified as *Calotropis procera* belonging to the family Apocynaceae. Various parts of the plant such as root, leaf, flower and latex are used medicinally. According to Ayurveda, Arka possesses Katu and Tikta rasa, Laghu, Ruksha and Tikshna guna, Ushna virya and Katu vipaka. It pacifies Kapha and Vata dosha while aggravating Pitta when used

excessively. Arka exhibits Dipana, Pachana, Krumighna, Shothahara, Lekhana and Kushtaghna properties. It is indicated in diseases such as Kustha, Arsha, Krimi, Shotha, Udara, Gulma and Vrana.

Snuhi is botanically identified as *Euphorbia neriifolia* Linn. of the family Euphorbiaceae. The latex, root and leaves are mainly used for therapeutic purposes. Snuhi possesses Katu and Tikta rasa, Laghu and Tikshna guna, Ushna virya and Katu vipaka. It alleviates Kapha and Vata dosha but increases Pitta. Pharmacologically, Snuhi acts as Bhedana, Rechana, Lekhana, Krumighna and Shothahara dravya. It is useful in the management of Udara roga, Arsha, Gulma, Krimi, Granthi and Shotha. Snuhi is an important ingredient of Snuhi Kshara and Ksharasutra preparations.

RESULTS

The review reveals that *Kacchuraksas Taila* comprises drugs predominantly having *Usna virya*, *Tikshna guna*, and *Kusthaghna–Krimighna* properties, processed in an oil base that enhances local penetration and therapeutic efficacy. Proper *Sodhana* and *Sneha Paka* play a crucial role in ensuring safety and efficacy. The formulation exhibits potential anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antipruritic, and wound-healing actions, making it useful in chronic dermatological conditions.

CONCLUSION

Kacchuraksas Taila is a potent classical Ayurvedic formulation with significant therapeutic value in skin and infectious disorders. Systematic documentation and scientific exploration of its pharmacological actions may help in promoting its rational, safe, and evidence-based clinical application. Further experimental and clinical studies are warranted to validate its traditional claims.

REFERENCES

1. Prof. Siddhinandan Mishra, Bhaishajyaratnavali of Kaviraj Govind das sen, Siddhiprada Hindi commentary, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan Varanasi, 2022, Chapter no. 54, Kushtha Rogadhikara, Shloka, 261-265: 890.
2. Tripathi, B. (2016), Sharangadhara Samhita (Madhyam Khanda 9/1-2) Chaukhamba Subharati Prakashan
3. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Haritakyadi Varga, Sloka, 151–152: 29–30.

4. Pt. Kashinath Shastri (2009), Rasatarangini of Shri Sadananda Sharma, Chaukhamba Sanskrit prakashan, Varanasi; Taranga 11, Sloka, 1–14: 215–218.
5. Pt. Kashinath Shastri (2009), Rasatarangini of Shri Sadananda Sharma, Chaukhamba Sanskrit prakashan, Varanasi; Taranga 11, Sloka, 15–28: 218–221.
6. Pt. Kashinath Shastri (2009), Rasatarangini of Shri Sadananda Sharma, Chaukhamba Sanskrit prakashan, Varanasi; Taranga 21, Sloka, 1–14: 520–523.
7. Pt. Kashinath Shastri (2009), Rasatarangini of Shri Sadananda Sharma, Chaukhamba Sanskrit prakashan, Varanasi, Taranga 8, Sloka 1–42: 124–132.
8. Pandit. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Lavaṇa Varga, Sloka, 1–3: 603–604.
9. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 196–197: 352.
10. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 88–89: 318.
11. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Haritakyadi Varga, Sloka, 47–48: 10–11.
12. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Haritakyadi Varga, Sloka, 32–34: 7–8.
13. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 162–163: 343.
14. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 122–124: 331.
15. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 141–142: 336.
16. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra(2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Haritakyadi Varga, Sloka, 69–70: 15.
17. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra(2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Haritakyadi Varga, Sloka, 92–94: 21.
18. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra(2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 154–156: 340.
19. Pt. Brahmasankara Mishra (2018), Bhavaprakasa Nighantu of Bhav Mishra, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Bhavan, Varanasi; Guduchyadi Varga, Sloka, 68–70: 314.